

Comprehensive mapping of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra

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Abstract

Tomato is a key horticultural crop in India, yet it is highly vulnerable to post-harvest losses across the supply chain. This study explores the structure of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra, one of India's leading tomato-producing states, and examines the major causes of food loss at various stages, from harvesting, storage, transportation, and retail to the customers. Based on literature from various regions of India, focusing on Maharashtra, the study identifies, for example, infrastructural, organizational, and market-related factors contributing to inefficiencies. Special attention is given to the role of middlemen and the fragmented nature of the supply chain. Potential interventions to reduce food loss include technological improvements in cold chain logistics, farmer training, policy measures such as contract farming, and value addition through tomato processing. The discussion highlights the need for region-specific solutions due to India's agricultural diversity, and the importance of supporting farmers economically to reduce food loss and improve supply chain resilience. Future research should focus on technology adoption feasibility, institutional reforms, and localized case studies to enable sustainable transformation in horticultural value chains.

Keywords:

tomato supply chain, food loss, post-harvest losses, Maharashtra, cold chain, horticulture, middlemen, agricultural policy, India

1. Introduction

Maharashtra is a leading state in the production of tomato in the whole country (Mookerjee & Wanmali, 2025). Vegetables are significant constituents of Indian agriculture and nutritional security due to their short duration, high yield, healthful richness, economic viability and capacity to create on-farm and off-farm employment (Nikam, 2020). With regard to agricultural land under tomato cultivation and tomato production, Nasik and Sangli districts are at forefront in the state (Nikam, 2020). However, during the last few decades agriculture losses have grown due to irregularity in monsoon and changes in climatic conditions over the Indian subcontinent, also in Maharashtra (Katalakute et al., 2016).

This research is about conducting a comprehensive mapping of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra utilising secondary data and literature reviews. This topic is highly relevant, as the impacts of inefficiencies in agricultural supply chains are wide-ranging, from economic losses for farmers to environmental burdens and food insecurity. Understanding these challenges in the context of Maharashtra is essential, especially given the state's prominent role in India's tomato production. Value chain includes a full range of activities from the production, distribution, processing, transporting and finally to the end consumer. Agriculture is the primary source of employment for two-thirds of the Indian population (Mohan et al., 2023). Maharashtra state is situated in the western and central parts of India. Maharashtra's capital, Mumbai is an island city on the western coast, connected to the mainland by roads and railways. (Mookerjee & Wanmali, 2025) Maharashtra is a leader among Indian states in terms of agricultural and industrial production, trade and transport, and education (Mookerjee & Wanmali, 2025).

Our aim is to understand various stages of the tomato supply chain in the region of Maharashtra and to identify critical factors contributing to wastage and losses within the supply chain. Investigating the potential applications of tomato farm-level agricultural residues and industrial by-products in the food sector in Maharashtra is very crucial as there are possibilities to enhance efficiency and reduce waste, ultimately improving economic

outcomes for farmers and ensuring better food availability in the region. The current global food system continues to struggle to provide healthy diets in the face of increasing environmental changes, highlighting the importance of understanding supply chains and ways to improve them (Boiteau & Bengali, 2022).

However, insufficient rainfall in much of Maharashtra is the main obstacle to agriculture in the state (Mookerjee & Wanmali, 2025), which can be explained by its subtropical to tropical (depending on elevation) climate and characteristically monsoonal nature, with local variations. Also, the progression from agricultural drought to socio-economic drought causes famine situations resulting in drought (Katalakute et al., 2016). Key issues also include inadequate storage facilities, poor transportation infrastructure, and inefficient harvesting techniques, which can lead to significant post-harvest losses (Nikam, 2020; Solunke, 2020)—reported as high as 30% for fruits and vegetables. Additionally, market dynamics, such as price fluctuations and the presence of middlemen, exacerbate these losses.

Finding solutions for such issues is an urgent need. The earning potential of tomato cultivation is proven to be even higher in previous research (Nikam, 2020), if these problems can be tackled. Any inefficiencies in these operations during various stages cause postharvest losses. This research aims to map the supply chain, and highlight areas for intervention that could enhance efficiency and reduce waste, ultimately improving economic outcomes for farmers and ensuring better food availability in the region. By identifying gaps and improvements in the supply chain of tomatoes, this research will contribute to building a more sustainable food system.

Research questions for the project are:

1. What are the different stages of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra?
2. At which stages of the supply chain do post-harvest losses occur, and what are the underlying causes?
3. What potential interventions could reduce food loss and improve the efficiency of the tomato supply chain?

The vision of this research is to support the development of a more sustainable and efficient tomato supply chain in Maharashtra by identifying where and why post-harvest losses occur, and by exploring practical ways to reduce them. By mapping the supply chain and highlighting underutilised agricultural residues and industrial by-products, this work aims to

provide actionable insights that can improve farmer incomes, reduce environmental burdens, and strengthen food availability in the region. The long-term goal is to inform policy and supply chain interventions that foster circular economy principles in agriculture and enhance resilience in regional food systems.

2. Methods

We conducted a literature review to examine the structure, dynamics, and inefficiencies in the tomato supply chain. Relevant information from each source was systematically summarised in notes and grouped according to their relevance to the three research questions. The data were then thematically analysed to identify key patterns related to supply chain structure, post-harvest losses, and utilisation of residues.

The review was based on secondary data and included peer-reviewed journal articles, government and institutional reports, academic theses. A comprehensive literature search was conducted using databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar, and AGRIS. In addition, official Indian government sources, including the Ministry of Agriculture and the Maharashtra State Agricultural Marketing Board, were consulted. Searches were carried out using keyword combinations such as "tomato supply chain", "post-harvest loss", "Maharashtra agriculture", "tomato waste", "agricultural residues" and "India". The search focused on literature published mainly from the year 2000 onwards, although a few earlier publications were included where deemed particularly relevant.

Studies were selected for inclusion based on their relevance to the tomato supply chain and food loss in Maharashtra or similar agro-climatic regions in India. Literature focusing on tomato production, supply chain structure, loss mechanisms, and biomass utilisation within the food system was prioritised. Sources that addressed only consumer preferences or marketing without a connection to supply chain dynamics or losses were excluded. Studies focusing solely on other crops were also excluded. As it was challenging to find only studies focusing on Maharashtra, studies considering other geographic areas were taken into account.

Relevant data were extracted and thematically analysed to identify critical points in the supply chain, types of losses, their underlying causes, and potential interventions. The findings are synthesised narratively to address the research questions and to provide a

comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra.

3. Results

3.1 Stages of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra

To understand the structure of the tomato supply chain and the points at which food loss occurs, the chain was first mapped into its main stages. Tomato is a horticultural crop that passes through several stages, including cultivation, harvesting, sorting and packaging, transportation, storage, and finally wholesale and retail before reaching consumers (Mohan et al., 2023).

3.1.1 Cultivation

Tomato cultivation in Maharashtra is shaped by specific climatic and environmental conditions. The state is one of India's largest producers of tomatoes, with districts such as Nashik and Sangli playing central roles (Nikam, 2020). However, cultivation is often challenged by monsoon dependency, drought, irregular rainfall, and pest outbreaks, which affect both yield quantity and quality (Katalakute et al., 2016; Anand, 2023). Limited access to irrigation and quality seeds further contributes to inefficiencies at this early stage.

3.1.2 Harvesting and initial handling

Harvesting is mostly manual and labour-intensive. Poor harvesting techniques and inadequate handling can lead to physical damage, reducing shelf life and increasing susceptibility to spoilage during later stages (Mohan et al., 2023). Anand (2023) reported that in the Vidarbha region in Maharashtra, 15–36% of tomatoes are lost already on the farm due to weather damage, pests, or management-related shortcomings.

3.1.3 Sorting, packaging, and transportation

After harvesting, tomatoes are sorted and packaged. However, inadequate packaging materials, lack of planning regarding purchase quantities, and excessive handling by multiple intermediaries, including producers, agents, and retailers, contribute significantly to post-harvest losses (Lebersorger et al., 2014). Transporting tomatoes across varying climate

zones without appropriate temperature control results in spoilage and loss of quality (Mohan et al., 2023). In India, produce is handled roughly and transported in the open atmosphere in trucks and it takes around twenty-four hours, and sometimes even more, to reach the retailer after harvesting (Negi et al., 2017), and therefore in these stages losses occur.

3.1.4 Storage

Although storage could be conceptually linked to earlier stages of the supply chain, it was frequently addressed as a separate stage in the literature. Therefore, I have treated it as an independent stage in this analysis. Proper storage of tomatoes requires temperatures between 10–15°C and 80–90 % relative humidity. However, such conditions are rarely maintained in Indian supply chains due to lack of cold chain infrastructure, especially in rural areas. (Mohan et al., 2023) According to their estimates, 20–40% of the tomato harvest is lost annually because of inadequate storage conditions. Similar findings were reported by Srikanta et al. (2017), who emphasized poor storage and transport infrastructure as major causes of post-harvest losses.

3.1.5 Wholesale and retail

At the retail level, tomatoes are often exposed to open air and harsh environmental conditions, further accelerating spoilage. Retail-level losses were found to be among the highest across horticultural crops, particularly due to quality degradation, lack of storage, and market volatility (Anand, 2023). When prices drop significantly, farmers may decide not to harvest their crops at all, as the cost of harvesting would not be recoverable, resulting in deliberate food waste during glut periods.

3.1.6 Structural and actor-based considerations

The tomato supply chain in Maharashtra also suffers from fragmentation, informal trade practices, and weak integration between actors (Hassan et al., 2020). The main stakeholders include farmers, collectors or traders, transporters, wholesalers, and retailers, each of whom adds complexity to the chain. Hassan et al. 2020 focus particularly on the actor network, while Mohan et al. emphasize operational aspects such as loading, unloading, and storage.

While the stages of the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra align with those identified across India (Mohan et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2020), regional climatic conditions, infrastructure

gaps, and actor-specific inefficiencies make Maharashtra a particularly revealing case for studying food loss in tomato cultivation.

3.2 Post-harvest losses

Post-harvest losses (PHL) in the tomato supply chain are extensive and occur across all stages following harvesting. These losses are attributed to multiple factors, including infrastructural limitations, climatic challenges, and market-related inefficiencies. Tomatoes are highly perishable and require carefully controlled storage conditions, specifically temperatures between 10–15°C and relative humidity of 80–90%. These conditions are seldom met due to the lack of a reliable cold chain infrastructure, especially in rural regions (Mohan et al., 2023). As a result, 20–40% of the tomato harvest is lost annually, primarily due to spoilage during transport and storage. Long-distance transportation across multiple climate zones without proper packaging or refrigeration further exacerbates quality degradation. Additional losses occur due to frequent handling, poor road infrastructure, and multiple checkpoints that delay the delivery of produce (Srikanta et al., 2017; Lebersorger et al., 2014).

Losses also occur at the farm level, where 15–36% of tomatoes may be lost due to pests, weather damage, and inadequate crop management practices, as observed by Anand (2023) in the Vidarbha region. These losses emerge even before tomatoes enter formal supply chains. In the retail phase, tomatoes are commonly sold in open-air markets, exposed to high temperatures and sunlight, which accelerates ripening and spoilage. Moreover, volatile market prices contribute to economic losses and food waste, as tomatoes are sometimes left unharvested when the price drops below the cost of harvesting (Anand, 2023; Mohan et al., 2023).

The structure of the supply chain itself contributes to inefficiencies. Involving multiple intermediaries such as traders, agents, and wholesalers, the chain is fragmented and lacks coordination, resulting in excessive handling, delays, and physical damage to the produce (Hassan et al., 2020; Lebersorger et al., 2014). Furthermore, only 1–2% of tomatoes are processed into value-added products such as sauces or purée, which exacerbates losses during peak harvest periods due to limited market absorption capacity.

Supply chain stage	Main loss causes	Key sources
Pre-harvest	Pests, weather events,	Anand (2023), Katalakute et al.

	poor input access	(2016)
Harvesting	Pests, weather events, poor input access	Mohan et al. (2023)
Packaging and sorting	Inadequate materials, improper sorting techniques	Lebersorger et al. (2014)
Transportation	No refrigeration, long distances, poor roads, excessive handling	Srikanta et al. (2017), Mohan et al. (2023); Negi et al., (2017)
Storage	Lack of cold storage, improper humidity and temperature control	Mohan et al. (2023)
Retail and wholesale	Open-air selling, no temperature control, unsold surplus due to low prices	Anand (2023), Hassan et al. (2020)

Table 2. Main causes for tomato losses in its supply chain

3.3 Potential interventions for reducing food loss and improving efficiency

The literature identifies several potential interventions to reduce food loss and enhance efficiency in the tomato supply chain, ranging from technological improvements to organizational reforms and policy-level changes. Technological solutions play a central role in mitigating post-harvest losses. Mohan et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of developing cold chain infrastructure, including technologies such as forced air cooling, evaporative cooling, ethylene management, and modified atmosphere storage. These technologies can significantly extend shelf life and reduce spoilage during transport and storage. Advanced methods like blast freezing, although effective, remain underutilized in India due to high initial costs and limited suitability for fresh produce.

Despite the availability of such technologies, implementation remains scarce in the Indian food supply chain. As Mohan et al. (2023) point out, there is a pressing need to identify the barriers to technology adoption and to assess the feasibility of scaling up available solutions in local contexts. Beyond technological fixes, organizational interventions are also critical. Contract farming is one such approach that can reduce market uncertainty, strengthen

linkages between farmers and buyers, and incentivize better production planning (Hassan et al., 2020). Similarly, training programs that focus on post-harvest handling, packaging, and storage practices have been shown to improve the quality and longevity of produce (Anand, 2023).

Policy instruments can also play a role in reducing inefficiencies. Price stabilization schemes, market information systems, and investment in local infrastructure such as rural roads and market facilities could help prevent overproduction and reduce losses during gluts. Developing local markets and shortening supply chains may further reduce the time tomatoes spend in transit, lowering spoilage rates.

Finally, circular economy strategies offer additional avenues to mitigate waste. As only a small fraction of tomatoes are currently processed, promoting the production of value-added products such as purées, sauces, and dried tomatoes could help absorb excess supply during peak seasons. Damaged or unsold tomatoes can also be diverted to animal feed or used in bioenergy production, thereby minimizing waste and providing alternative revenue streams for farmers and supply chain actors.

4. Discussion

This literature review examined the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra, with a particular focus on the stages where post-harvest losses occur and potential interventions to reduce inefficiencies. The findings indicate that food loss is present across all stages of the value chain, beginning already at cultivation and extending through to the retail level. These losses are not only technical but also deeply embedded in the economic and institutional structure of the food system.

One of the central observations is that value chain assessments for horticultural crops must take a more holistic view that includes both pre- and post-harvest losses. Horticulture is highly labour-intensive and involves a wide range of actors, from farmers to middlemen, wholesalers, and retailers, all of whom influence the quantity and quality of the produce as it moves through the chain (Nolan, 2004). The actions of intermediaries, particularly middlemen, play a crucial role in shaping both price formation and physical losses. Multiple handling points and inadequate infrastructure are compounded by the presence of these intermediaries, often leading to inefficiencies and even exploitative pricing dynamics. One of

the key contributors to quality issues is the lack of temperature-controlled transportation, followed by impacts during transit, inconsistent packaging box standards, compression, excessive load, overloading, and improper stacking (Negi et al., 2017), not to mention the poor road conditions.

While the general structure of the tomato supply chain appears similar across India, regional differences are significant. Maharashtra, as one of the country's leading tomato-producing states, presents specific vulnerabilities, such as high dependence on monsoon rains, fragmented market systems, and frequent climate shocks. These conditions make localized analysis especially important. However, a clear gap in the literature was the lack of region-specific studies, many analyses took a pan-Indian approach, which risks overlooking the highly uneven agroecological and socioeconomic conditions between states.

From a farmer's perspective, price volatility is among the most critical challenges. Due to oversupply during harvest peaks and the absence of adequate processing or storage facilities, market prices often crash to uneconomical levels. As a result, farmers sometimes leave produce unharvested because harvesting and transportation would cost more than the income received. This issue underscores the urgent need for mechanisms such as price stabilization schemes, contract farming, and improved market access to reduce the economic risk borne by producers (Hassan et al., 2020).

Moreover, awareness of post-harvest management techniques remains low among many small-scale tomato farmers. Although technologies such as forced-air cooling or modified atmosphere storage exist, adoption remains minimal due to cost, lack of technical training, and insufficient supply chain coordination (Mohan et al., 2023). This reflects a broader issue: reducing food loss is not just about infrastructure, but also about information and organization. Training programs, access to reliable market data, and institutional support systems are equally essential.

The role of horticulture in India is gaining increasing attention as a potential engine of rural and regional development, especially in the face of growing climate uncertainty, declining farm incomes, and population pressure. Diversification toward high-value crops such as tomatoes can increase income potential for smallholders, but only if value chain inefficiencies and post-harvest losses are addressed comprehensively.

5. Conclusion and future directions

This study has examined the tomato supply chain in Maharashtra with a focus on identifying the key stages where food loss occurs and the interventions that could reduce inefficiencies. The analysis confirms that losses are widespread and occur throughout the supply chain, from pre-harvest to retail. These losses are driven by both technical and systemic challenges, including insufficient cold chain infrastructure, price volatility, limited processing options, and the structural fragmentation of the value chain.

While the reviewed literature provides a strong foundation for understanding the dynamics of tomato post-harvest loss, there remains a notable gap in region-specific research. Most studies focus on India as a whole, overlooking the agroecological and socioeconomic diversity between states. Maharashtra's case illustrates the need for localized approaches that consider both the physical and institutional environments affecting food loss.

Effective solutions must go beyond technological fixes. Although improved storage, transportation, and processing technologies are crucial, their success depends on affordability, farmer awareness, and institutional support. Organisational interventions, such as strengthening farmer-market linkages and reducing dependency on middlemen, can further improve supply chain resilience. Policy mechanisms like price stabilization and contract farming are also essential to mitigate economic risks for farmers and reduce food waste caused by market fluctuations.

Future research could focus on the following questions. First, it is essential to identify regionally appropriate post-harvest technologies and understand the barriers that prevent their adoption, such as cost, lack of awareness, or infrastructural limitations. Second, further investigation is needed into institutional dynamics, particularly how market structures and the role of middlemen contribute to inefficiencies and food loss, and how these systems could be reformed to support more equitable and efficient supply chains. Third, more localized, crop-specific case studies are necessary to account for the significant agroecological and socioeconomic variation across India, which affects how challenges and solutions manifest in different regions.

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